

${}^4T_{1g}(P)$, 10000 cm^{-1} [${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$], 17756 cm^{-1} [${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$], 26030 cm^{-1} [${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$] and 11780 cm^{-1} [${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$], 19380 cm^{-1} [${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$], 27010 cm^{-1} [${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$], respectively. The complexes of Cr(III) and Mn(III) show four bands in their electronic spectra appearing at 14250 cm^{-1} [${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3E_g$], 18400 cm^{-1} [${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$], 23270 cm^{-1} [${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$], 38400 cm^{-1} [${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$] and 11000 cm^{-1} [${}^6B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6B_{2g}$], 13200 cm^{-1} [${}^6B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}$], 17980 cm^{-1} [${}^6B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6E_g$], 29580 cm^{-1} [${}^6B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6E_g$], respectively. The values of β of these complexes indicate the partial covalent character of the metal-ligand bond.

Infrared spectral data for the ligand and its complexes are given in Table 3. $\nu(C=N)$, $\nu(CH=N)$ and $\nu(C=O)$ are lowered on complex formation by 15 to 45 units indicating that these groups are participating in chelation. Bands appearing at 250 cm^{-1} and 275 cm^{-1} in Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes, respectively are assignable to metal-chlorine stretching mode⁶.

References

1. R. C. SAXENA, C. L. JAIN, S. C. RASTOGI and H. S. VERMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16A, 167.
2. H. S. VERMA and R. C. SAXENA, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1978, 33b, 1001.
3. H. S. VERMA and R. C. SAXENA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1978, 47, 791.
4. G. SCHWARZBAUM, "Complexometric Titrations", Interscience, New York, 1957.
5. D. F. MALLOR and L. MALKY, *Nature*, 1948, 159, 370.

Azo Complexes : Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of Some Organic Acids with *o*-hydroxybenzeneazo-2-Naphthol

A. K. BANERJEE, TARKESHWAR SINGH and S. K. ROY
 Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005
Manuscript received 26 October 1981, accepted 8 July 1982

A series of mixed ligand adducts of alkali metal salts of different organic acids with *o*-hydroxybenzeneazo-2-naphthol, of the general formula

ML.OHBAN (M = Li, Na or K; L = deprotonated organic acids; 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, *o*-nitrophenol, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, salicylic acid, salicylaldehyde; OHBAN = *o*-hydroxybenzeneazo-2-naphthol), have been synthesised. The adducts have been judged by their analytical results and infrared spectra, and this throws light on the fact that one molecule of alkali metal salt of organic acid combines with one molecule of ligand OHBAN, suggesting coordination number five or six for the metal atom.

Experimental

The ligand OHBAN was prepared by standard method¹, m.p. 194° . All the alkali metal salts used were prepared in 95% ethanol.

The general method of preparation was to take the hot absolute alcoholic solution of OHBAN and to add to it the alkali metal salts of organic acids in mono-molecular ratio. The whole mixture in solution was refluxed over water bath with stirring for about 1 hr. The solution, on keeping, yielded crystalline solid adducts. The crystals were filtered, washed with absolute alcohol and dried in an oven at 80° .

Results and Discussion

The adducts are stable when stored under dry condition e.g. in a desiccator. All the complexes are coloured (green, dark violet or brown). The compounds are thermally stable. When heated, they undergo a decomposition at a temperature higher than the melting point of the ligand. The adducts break on heating to form the simple salts and ligand, and this indicates that the bonding in these compounds is not strong. The colour, melting or decomposition temperatures and analysis of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The presence of two -OH groups in the *o, o'* positions to the azo group may increase the coordinating capacity of -N=N- group. It also suggests the possibility of intra-molecular hydrogen bonding due to which the metal is complexed in cyclic form.

TABLE 1

Compound	Colour	Melting / Decomp. temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	Found (%)				Calcd. (%)			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
OHBAN=L	Deep violet	194 m	72.69	4.55	10.61	—	72.72	4.54	10.60	—
Na1N2N.L	Dark violet	220 d	68.14	3.89	8.95	5.16	68.00	3.92	9.15	5.01
K1N2N.L	Dark violet	210 d	65.51	3.69	8.39	8.85	65.78	3.79	8.84	8.21
Na8HQ.L	Deep brown	250 d	70.48	4.10	9.51	5.09	70.40	4.06	9.48	5.19
K8HQ.L	Deep brown	215 d	67.92	3.94	9.48	8.14	68.00	3.92	9.35	8.50
NaONP.L	Green	233 d	62.09	3.81	9.95	5.40	62.12	3.76	9.88	5.41
KONP.L	Green	212 d	60.15	3.59	9.68	8.21	60.00	3.62	9.52	8.84
Na2H3NA.L	Brownish green	295 d	68.42	4.15	6.24	4.69	68.35	4.22	5.90	4.85
K2H3NA.L	Brownish green	290 d	66.42	3.91	6.11	7.59	66.12	3.88	5.71	8.00
Kacac.L	Green	208 d	62.92	4.45	5.82	9.95	62.68	4.72	6.96	9.70
Na.anth.L	Deep red	220 d	65.41	4.04	9.99	5.04	65.24	4.25	9.90	5.43
K.anth.L	Green	210 d	62.56	4.22	9.79	8.22	62.87	4.10	9.57	8.88
NaSalH.L	Brown	255 d	67.82	4.09	6.91	5.31	67.64	4.16	6.86	5.62
KSalH.L	Brown	242 d	64.92	4.12	6.98	8.75	65.10	4.00	6.60	9.20

OHBAN = *o*-hydroxybenzeneazo-2-naphthol, 1N2N = 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8HQ = 8-hydroxyquinoline, ONP = *o*-nitrophenol, 2H3NA = 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, acac = acetylacetone, anth = anthranilic acid, SalH = salicylaldehyde.

Cenni *et al*² have reported that azo frequencies were usually observed in the range of 1570-1595 cm^{-1} . Bands in the region 1472-1545 cm^{-1} have been attributed to a number of aryl azo compounds of Mo by King³. In the ligand OHBAN, we obtain the $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ band at 1550 cm^{-1} . In the adducts, this band shifts down to 1540-1515 cm^{-1} suggesting that the $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ group is probably associated to the metal. These bands also split in the adducts which may be due to a change in symmetry. The $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ frequency of ligand and its compounds with alkali metal salts have been given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SELECTED IR FREQUENCIES OF LIGAND AND ADDUCTS

Compound	$-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ frequency (cm^{-1})
OHBAN=L	1550
NaIN2N.L	1540, 1585 ¹
KIN2N.L	1540, 1585
NaSHQ.L	1540, 1585
KSHQ.L	1535, 1580
NaONP.L	1540
KONP.L	1540
Na2H3NA.L	1535
K2H3NA.L	1535, 1530
Na.anth.L	1525, 1510
K.anth.L	1545, 1535
NaSalH.L	1540, 1525

The OH stretching frequency of the ligand has been observed at $\sim 3360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. It shifts down to $\sim 3220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the compounds thereby showing the involvement of $-\text{OH}$ in the formation of adducts. The $\text{H}-\text{O}-\text{H}$ bending mode is seen at $\sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand, while in the compounds two peaks at $\sim 1320-1310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $\sim 1280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed. The extra peaks in complexes may justify their formation.

References

1. BRILSTEIN-PRAGER JACOBSON, "Org. Chemie", Band 16, System No. 2085-2358, 160.
2. CENNI *et al*, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1971, 3411.
3. R. B. KING, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 300.

Conductometric and Spectrometric Studies on Complexes of Ag(I) and Hg(II) Ions with N,N'-Diphenyl Thiourea

B. SINGH, UMA SHANKAR PRASAD SHARMA
and

D. K. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, Patna University,
Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 3 June 1980, revised 25 March 1982,
accepted 21 July 1982

SINCE N,N'-diphenylthiourea contains two phenyl substituent groups, the complexation behaviour of this ligand decreases¹⁻³ because of the electron withdrawing tendency of the phenyl group. In

view of this, complexing behaviour of this ligand with Ag(I) and Hg(II) ions have been investigated in solution by conductometric titration and in solid state by infrared spectroscopy and the results are reported here.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. N,N'-Diphenylthiourea was prepared by standard method⁴. The prepared compound gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

Preparation of complexes: The diaquo N,N'-diphenylthiourea silver(I) nitrate polymeric complex, $\{[\text{Ag}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{DPhTU})]\text{NO}_3\}_n$, was prepared by simply mixing an aqueous solution of AgNO_3 with ethanolic solution of N,N'-diphenylthiourea in 1:2 molar ratio. A green coloured precipitate formed immediately which was digested on water bath for 30 min. The complex was thereafter filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried at 110° . (Found: C, 35.90; H, 3.45; N, 9.41; Ag, 24.84. Calcd. C, 35.94; H, 3.69; N, 9.69; Ag, 24.90%).

The green aquochloro N,N'-diphenylthiourea mercury(II) chloride complex, $\{[\text{Hg}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{DPhTU})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}\}_n$, was prepared in the same manner as the Ag(I) complex. (Found: N, 5.84; Cl 13.43; Hg, 39.2%. Calcd. N, 5.41; Cl, 13.72; Hg, 39.8%).

Physical methods: The magnetic measurements were made at 30° using Guoy Balance. Both the complexes were found to be diamagnetic. The infrared spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using Perkin Elmer spectrophotometers, Model 521 and 621 in the range $4000-200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Conductometric titrations were carried out by means of Toshniwal conductometric bridge, model 302 using a dip type cell (cell constant $1.92 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mho/cm}^2$).

Results and Discussion

The analytical results indicate that empirical formula of the solid complexes are $\text{Ag}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{DPhTU})\text{NO}_3$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{DPhTU})\text{Cl}_2$. The conductometric titrations of 0.01 M AgNO_3 and 0.01 M HgCl_2 solutions were conducted against 0.005 M diphenyl urea solution and inflexion points for both titrations indicate the formation of 1:1 complexes.

The Ag(I) complex contains ionic nitrate. This has been confirmed by chemical method as well as by the infrared spectra of the complex. The infrared spectra of this complex exhibit a strong band at 1385 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 845 cm^{-1} . These bands are not present in the spectra of the diphenylthiourea ligand or of the Hg(II) complex. Since ionic nitrates exhibit⁵ strong infrared bands in the range of $1340-1410 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and weak band in the range of $800-860 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, it may be suggested that nitrate group is in the ionic form in the Ag(I) complex. But as the complex is insoluble in almost all organic solvents, it may be tentatively assigned a polymeric